

Impediments to Adult Learner Engagement in Higher Education Mathematics Learning: Obstacles to Creating a Classroom Culture of Enquiry

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Learner engagement with mathematics can oftentimes be sporadic and reactive, but in the context of non-traditional, (part-time, undergraduate) adult learners, perhaps more so. This paper outlines some key areas for investigation and research, begins to outline some of the key literature and theoretical perspectives whilst at all times considering impediments that hinder adult engagement with mathematical learning – both individually and corporately. Moreover, it discusses the hypothesis that learners who disengage do so over time and occupy a series of three zones or so-called ‘coping states’, which appear to exist within a continuum characterised as reticent, retreating and withdrawn. It is further hypothesised specific, situational triggers exist, which impede learning and precipitate disengagement, and if identified, may be mitigated or ameliorated. The paper’s function is to provide the reader with an overview of the study thus far undertaken, the key hypotheses identified and subsequent research questions in advance of undertaking the review of theoretical perspectives and key literature.

Creating a Classroom Culture: Dialogic Teaching and Learning

The genesis for this research derives from many years’ experience of teaching and observing adult learners’ difficulties learning mathematics in higher education. Struggles with articulating their mathematical thinking, in addition to much greater difficulties communicating with each other and their instructor were most obvious and disheartening. Learners appeared oftentimes incapable of being understood as they intended, whilst acting as if mathematical language usage was the preserve only of the teacher and not germane to them. Apparently, they did not see the need to appropriate the exemplars of the teacher. Equally, when in small group or whole class discussions, the obvious nervousness or awkwardness felt by some self-conscious adults speaking corporately seemed to exacerbate their rejection of apposite mathematical language. Some reverted to common, everyday colloquialisms, including slang words instead of clear, concise, communication utilising appropriate jargon. Often, this resulted in learners becoming frustrated – sometimes with themselves, other times with their peers and occasionally with their instructor – worryingly, some learners disengaged from the learning subsequently, and decoupled from their groups when collaborating. Re-engaging such learners I found to be quite difficult; and once I noticed some learners criticising and blaming one another for their lack of progress, I resolved to investigate potential solutions for mitigation.

There are instances within the literature e.g. see (Goos, 2002) and (Mason and Johnston-Wilder, 2006) whereby teacher-researchers have attempted to discern the kernel of establishing an environment where mathematical thinking is articulated corporately within

classrooms and amongst peers. The focus of my research will involve overlaps with these researchers as well as others such as Schoenfeld's seminal research from 1983 onwards.

Furthermore, (Alexander, 2020, p.1) argues that language is at the heart of learning, an assertion supported by emancipatory constructivists such as (Freire, 1970) and (Mezirow, 1991). Alexander describes it this way:

“In its pursuit of the metalinguistic alongside the communicative, dialogic teaching is **more** than just ‘classroom talk’. It is as distinct from the question-answer and listen-repeat routines which most of us experienced as school as it is from everyday conversation, aiming to be more **consistently searching and reciprocal** than both” (emphasis added).

Social classroom interactions in a reciprocal, dialogic fashion mediates socially constructed learning. If mathematical articulation such as self-talk, peer-to-peer talk, and classroom talk are being discussed then the topic of dialogic teaching should be considered. Therefore, the literature so far has assisted me in deriving the following hypotheses, which have in turn led to the research question(s).

One hypothesis is that poor or reduced learner articulation negatively affects classroom communication, mathematical thinking, and collaboration, impeding self-regulation and metacognition, and opposes the formation of a metacognitive and dialogic classroom culture. Moreover, improved learner articulation mediates improved communication, which in turn, leads to improved mathematical thinking, or at least mediates foundations for establishing a metacognitive classroom culture of enquiry. (Mason and Johnston-Wilder, 2006, p.37) have referred to this phenomenon in another way, namely the so-called ‘conjecturing atmosphere’. They describe it as an atmosphere

“...[where] anybody can be asked to explain their thinking so as to try to convince others. Thus when two people disagree, each can try to persuade the other, ..., thereby initiating mathematical thinking.”

A further hypothesis is that learners who disengage from learning mathematics do so in a nuanced way and it appears such disengagement is a process, not unlike a sliding scale or a continuum, with degrees of disengagement. One working hypothesis is that this continuum may be categorised into at least three distinct zones or so-called ‘coping states’: reticent, retreating, and withdrawn, i.e. the *reticent-retreating-withdrawn (RRW) continuum*, through which disengagement is mediated.

Moreover, classroom culture, teacher role-modelling of mathematical articulation and language, are also relevant. How can dialogic teaching improve engagement for, or at the very least, remove impediments preventing anxious learners engaging in mathematical learning? It seems to me that a *culture of enquiry* within the classroom, championed by the teacher, is one obvious solution - see (Goos, 2002 and 2004). It seems both interesting and fitting to consider carefully therefore, any effect of a reciprocal, dialogical teaching and learning paradigm established within a classroom culture of enquiry, interfacing with adult learners on the *reticent-retreating-withdrawn (RRW) continuum*. Therefore, the main research question currently is stated as:

What impediments exist which diminish adult learner engagement in mathematics and corrupt communication between learners and instructor, and interfere with collaborative learning of mathematics?

Subsequent, related research questions include:

- a) What might hinder, impede or be antagonistic to the learning of mathematics collaboratively? Are there specific settings in, or specific triggers with which learners are hindered in their collaboration and/or learning? Is mathephobia a factor?
- b) How might these impediments be ameliorated or mitigated? What role might metacognitive control play in learners being facilitated towards metacognitive collaboration?
- c) With reference to the establishing of a collaborative metacognitive community of enquiry, how might learners mediate, preserve, and ultimately perpetuate such a paradigm? What provides an impetus that spurs on learning in this way? Are there specific catalysts for impetus?

Understanding the Adult Learner of Mathematics - Affective and Other Characteristics

Learner Cohort

The learner cohort in consideration comprised mainly self-funded adult learners i.e. over 18 years of age, and who have concluded their traditional school obligations. Some will have completed secondary schooling to Leaving Certificate standard, whilst others will have varying levels of schooling, terminating at various stages. Levels of attainment will vary, accordingly.

All are engaged in a one-semester Engineering Mathematics module, taken as part of an overall programme which ultimately provides a level 6 Higher Certificate in Engineering. It is worth noting this cohort differs to so-called 'mature students' within the Irish educational system; these learners are over-18, studying part-time, usually evening-attending, rather than full-time students over the age of 23 years, pursuing level 6-8 programmes.

Learner Mathematical Background

Learners present with varying levels of mathematical ability and past success. Over the years, much of the cohort presents with similar characteristics. For example, they are usually in full or part-time employment, perhaps working shifts and may be absent for one or more sessions as a result and are predominantly male. Mathematical anxiety is present throughout this cohort and typically, depends on age, surprisingly. It appears that the length of time since traditional schooling ended is a determining factor in whether mathematical anxiety is likely to manifest. Research by (Multon et al, 1991) and (Lanigan, 2007) found that self-efficacy and performance were affected to a greater extent for older adult learners and low achieving adult learners.

Moving forward, it will be instructive to highlight key general characteristics of adult learners, their motivations for learning as adults, and differences in comparison to traditional students. Participation is, in the main, voluntary and for an intended purpose. Pressure may exist in those situations where learners may be pursuing programmes for CPD reasons and

participation may be less than voluntary. In many cases the learner has an agenda to achieve some learning goal that may be linked to employment or career prospects, where employers may have some vested interest, whilst others simply have social reasons, or for self-actualisation. A majority of adult learners will have had some experience of traditional schooling. Continuing Education is understood by (Rogers, 2007, p.35) as “relatively advanced professionally oriented programmes for adults who have already been educated”. Continuing education therefore includes those adult learners whose experiences are other than traditional, and undoubtedly, the evening classrooms and lecture theatres of higher education institutes are a nexus predominated by such cohorts.

Additionally, key characteristic differences are acknowledged which help to separate the adult learner from the learner as a child - it is remarkable that not all characteristics need to be present for an adult to be defined. Adults are self-recognising and recognise other adults; self-determined, fully grown, developed, and moving towards greater maturity. If children are ‘growing up’, then according to (Rogers, 2007, pp.40-41), adults are ‘grown ups’ and have ‘arrived’.

In terms of perspective, adults have a more balanced approach to life, having some sense of far-sightedness, and tend not to act childishly, however adults can act like children, notably in education settings. Adults have responsibilities, managing their own lives and perhaps the lives of others such as dependents. They usually possess autonomy and are relatively secure. In terms of diversity, individuals are different and come to learning with different motivations and life experiences, affiliations and expectations. Children generally tend to flock together and stand out less in the crowd.

Adult learners have different motivations for entering academia to traditional school-leavers. Generally, adults are more self-directed and focussed and quite determined and somewhat resilient due to life-experience. Maturity is an obvious difference between these cohorts and (Perry, 1970), illustrates the journey of development and maturation (intellectually at least) of traditional learners through their college years. It is worth noting that most students traditionally attain so-called ‘adulthood’ whilst attending college, however, it does not mean they are considered ‘adult learners’, as the term applies.

(Rogers, 2007, p.15), argues adult learners in general, engage in (to varying degrees) a so-called ‘learning contract’ with the learning provider, the terms of which may be made explicit or not, but an implicit ‘bargain has been struck’ nonetheless between learner and provider. In contemporary times we are seeing more and more often the student as customer and the customer has found the complaints department especially when they feel their expectations have not been met.

Nonetheless, despite the much lauded and oft reported ‘experience’ adults bring to academia, it remains a two-edged sword: along with life experience, adults also bring forms of ‘baggage’ with them into the classroom, mainly relating to their previous negative experiences. Often they have been conditioned into an unrealistic expectation of a didactic pedagogy that leaves them feeling lost, confused and disappointed. Research by (Meltzer,

2002) and (Zopp, 1999) amongst others, found that previous mathematical experience as well as ‘trigger events’ related to mathematics education contributed towards mathematics anxiety in adult learners.

Particularly in mathematics learning, mistake-making is disliked intensely because it is perceived as a form of ‘stupidity’ by many adult learners. Mistakes are to be avoided, and if made, are to remain hidden and undivulged; such dysfunctionality, it is hypothesised, impedes learning significantly in adults. Moreover, (Lanigan, 2007, pp.22-23) found older adults particularly held beliefs that their ‘school’ mathematics was now superseded by ‘new’ mathematics – essentially, they viewed their own mathematical capital as near to worthless in the current setting. The research of both (Skemp, 1971) – *understanding mathematics relationally versus instrumentally* – and (Ernest, 2004) – *absolutist versus fallibilist philosophies in mathematics* – seem to be germane and have consonance with the overall research

There is, consequently, a number of resulting hypotheses; the first is mathephobia manifests in adult learners of mathematics and is mediated through inability or reticence to coherently communicate with other learners and instructor. Several potential causes are identifiable: anecdotally, resorting to negative talk (self, peer-to-peer, or with instructor) is a clear indication of poor or reduced mathematical self-efficacy and self-image, potentially indicating moderate to high levels of mathematical anxiety.

It is further hypothesised that undiagnosed or hidden levels of mathematical anxiety in adult learners mediates disengagement. Such anxiety may reveal itself in a number of ways, including the manner in which adult learners deal with mistake-making, for example.

Adult Learner Resistance to Learning Mathematics

Learner resistance to learning in higher education is a deceptively complex and multi-faceted phenomenon that has remained relatively misdiagnosed or ill-defined within the literature, according to (Tolman and Kremling, 2017, p.3), who researched cohorts of mature nursing students in higher education and described the aetiology of student resistance with their *IMSR (integrated model of student resistance)* see Figure 1. They define student resistance as “...an outcome, a motivational state in which students reject learning opportunities due to systemic factors”. They go on to emphasise the point that resistance is a motivational state, an outcome of multiple interacting factors, as opposed to a trait that endures over time or exists as part of a student’s personality.

Furthermore, they go on to describe the difficulties instructors encounter when introducing a much more active learning paradigm within their classrooms. Clearly, there is potential for this current research to propose one or more solutions which mitigate learner resistance in spite of the typically didactic pedagogical expectations of many adult learners undertaking higher education. It is noteworthy (Tolman and Kremling, 2017) have identified within their research a form of passive resistance with learner characteristics not too dissimilar to those of a disengaged learner who could be situated on the *RRW-continuum*, most likely *withdrawn*.

The subsequent hypothesis is, that adult learner resistance to learning mathematics may in fact be ‘signal’ rather than ‘noise’, as (Tolman and Kremling, 2017) found, and just as their findings on student resistance appear to indicate a fluid, reactive nature to the phenomenon, it is further hypothesised there exist similarities with the coping states within the *RRW-continuum*, most notably *withdrawn*, with mathematical anxiety being involved or at least interacting in some form, perhaps from past negative experiences, instigating learners to ultimately withdraw from learning. It is hypothesised that the *RRW-continuum* as a phenomenon is equally fluid, dynamic and most certainly reactive in nature. It is hypothesised the *RRW-continuum* is a more nuanced interpretation of student resistance. The resulting research question is as follows:

In terms of adult learner motivation, what impact might learner self-efficacy, conation, learner resistance and mathematical anxiety have on engagement, collaboration, and mathematical thinking, and in mitigating impediments?

Subsequent, related research questions include:

- a) What evidence might exist for adult learner engagement with (some or all of) negative self-talk, negative peer-to-peer talk and/or negative talk towards or from the instructor? What role, if any, does learner self-efficacy play?
- b) If so, what type of negative talk exists, and might it be triggered by certain cues or events? Might it be possible to categorise such triggering events, and might they be typified in some way?
- c) What relationship, if any, exists between adult learner self-efficacy and negative self-talk? What effect might this have on collaborative learning in adults? Might there be some effect on adult learner participation (especially learners on the reticent-retreating-withdrawn continuum) in a collaborative learning context?
- d) What are the effects of mathematical anxiety (also known as mathophobia) on adult learners and in a collaborative context? If anxiety manifests, what is the nature of the manifestation? Is learner resistance, for example, a key indicator of undiagnosed or hidden mathematical anxiety in adult learners?
- e) If learners resist learning or engaging, what might be the root cause(s) of such behaviour?

Figure 1

Integrated Model of Student Resistance (IMSR)

References

Alexander, R. (2020). *A dialogic teaching companion* (1st ed.). Routledge.

Ernest, P. (2004). *Philosophy of mathematics education journal* edited by Paul Ernest. http://Www.People.Ex.Ac.Uk/PErnest/Pome18/PhoM_%20for_ICME_04.Htm. <http://socialsciences.exeter.ac.uk/education/research/centres/stem/publications/pmej/>

Goos, M. (2002). Understanding metacognitive failure. *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 21(3), 283–302. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0732-3123\(02\)00130-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0732-3123(02)00130-x)

Goos, M. (2004). Learning mathematics in a classroom community of inquiry. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 35(4), 258. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30034810>

Lanigan, M. (2007). *The effects of learner self-confidence on competence in mathematics* (Master’s dissertation). Waterford Institute of Technology. <https://repository.wit.ie/3400/1/Dissertation%20FINAL>

Mason, J., & Johnston-Wilder, S. (2006). *Designing and using mathematical tasks* (None ed.). Tarquin Group.

Meltzer, D. E. (2002). The relationship between mathematics preparation and conceptual learning gains in physics: A possible “hidden variable” in diagnostic pretest scores. *American Journal of Physics*, 70(12), 1259–1268. <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.1514215>

Mezirow, J. (1991). *Transformative dimensions of adult learning* (1st ed.). Jossey-Bass.

Multon, K. D., Brown, S. D., & Lent, R. W. (1991). Relation of self-efficacy beliefs to academic outcomes: A meta-analytic investigation. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 38(1), 30–38. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0167.38.1.30>

- Perry, W. (1970). *Forms of ethical and intellectual development in the college years: A scheme* (1st ed.). Holt, Rinehart & Winston.
- Rogers, A. (2007). *Teaching adults* (3rd ed.). Open University Press.
- Schoenfeld, A. H. (2016). Learning to think mathematically: Problem solving, metacognition, and sense making in mathematics (Reprint). *Journal of Education*, 196(2), 1–38.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/002205741619600202>
- Skemp, R. R. (1971). *The psychology of learning mathematics* (1st ed.). Harmondsworth.
- Tolman, A. O., Kremling, J., & Tagg, J. (2016). *Why students resist learning: A practical model for understanding and helping students* (Reprint ed.). Stylus Publishing.
- Zopp, M. A. (1999). *Math anxiety, the adult student and the community college* (Ed. D. Dissertation). Northern Illinois University.
<https://www.proquest.com/openview/7a5e951615662118a0145b6803a43814/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>